

Conservation challenges of Lesser Adjutant stork (*Leptoptilos javanicus*) of Nagaon, assam

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Nagaon, a place of rich biodiversity and habitat consists of a number of species. The Lesser Adjutant stork (*Leptoptilos javanicus*) is one of them but as other species it has got several conservation challenges. The LAS is also alarmingly declined day by day and declare near threatened by IUCN. The challenges that come with the conservation of these species are infrastructural development, road construction, decline in the water level of Kolong river which also affects this bird habitat loss etc. The study was carried out from September, 2023 to February, 2024 in Dimoruguri, Nagaon, Assam. The study revealed that the bird was facing danger from various angles like chopping the trees, destruction of their nesting trees, habitat degradation, killing by the unknown people. Proper conservation measures are needed for proper conservation of the bird species like to protect its breeding colonies i.e by protecting its nesting trees. Hunting should be banned and the local villagers should be trained by organizing proper awareness programs. Again, as this is a water dependent species so the conservation of Kolong river flowing by the side of nesting trees will also be a major point in proper conservation of the species. Safeguarding remaining populations from extinction can help in proper conservation of the species.

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